

Shifting Lithium Amide Reactivity to the Radical Domain: Regioselective Radical C-H Functionalization of 3-Iodooxetane for the Synthesis of 1,5-Dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes

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Abstract: Strained spiro-heterocycles (SSH) have gained significant attention within the medicinal chemistry community as promising (sp^3)-rich bioisosteres for their aromatic and non-spirocyclic counterparts. We herein report access to an unprecedented spiro-heterocycle - 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane. Our synthetic approach leverages a lithium-amide induced single-electron transfer to benzophenones generating an *N*-centered radical and a ketyl radical anion - reminiscent of a frustrated radical pair. This pair works synergistically to selectively abstract the β -hydrogen from 3-iodooxetane, initiating an exergonic radical-radical coupling reaction. This process enables the formation of the desired bond between the oxetane core and benzophenone derivatives, ultimately yielding the novel 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane core. The stability and synthetic utility of the novel 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane motif are showcased. An in-depth mechanistic investigation is presented, including cyclic voltammetry studies, as well as computational calculations and experiments to support the mechanism of this new single electron synthetic tactic.

Introduction

With the ongoing search for hitherto unexplored chemical space, (strained) spiro-heterocycles have garnered significant attention.^[1–5] Such structurally rigid and sp^3 -rich motifs populate, in contrast to their flat aromatic counterparts, a third dimension

which can impart improved biological and physicochemical properties on drug candidates, including metabolic stability, decreased lipophilicity or increased solubility.^[6,7] Thus, this exit from “molecular flatland” towards drug candidates more densely populated with three-dimensional moieties has been positively correlated with a lower attrition rate of transitioning drug candidates from discovery through clinical trials,^[8] due to higher target selectivity, and superior toxicity- and pharmacokinetic profiles.^[9] Development of such strained spiro-heterocycles focused for a large part on the synthesis of motifs containing at least one four-membered ring, which provides highly predictable exit vectors emanating from the well-defined spatial location of the substituents.^[10–12] Thus, in recent years the chemical community has witnessed a rise in the development of new strained spiro-heterocycles with a particular focus on the spiro[3.3]heptane motif and its various heteroatom-containing derivatives (i.e., 2-oxa-6-azaspiro[3.3]heptane and others in **Figure 1, A**),^[13–26] some of which are being incorporated into lead compounds or drug candidates currently undergoing clinical trials.^[26–28]

Although not yet validated as bioisosteres, their “contracted” spiro[2.3]hexane derivatives recently garnered, based on their high ring strain, significant interest as versatile compounds in organic synthesis. For example, epoxide-bearing 1-oxaspiro[2.3]hexane^[29–31] and 1-oxa-5-azaspiro[2.3]hexane^[32–34]

motifs have recently been reported (**Figure 1, B**). Both motifs are accessible *via* comparable synthetic approaches, consisting of intramolecular strain-release driven epoxidation of “spring-loaded” carbon-carbon or carbon-nitrogen bridgehead bonds of bicyclo[1.1.0]butane- and azabicyclo[1.1.0]butane-substituted carbinols, respectively. Despite these advances, the synthesis of the oxetane-containing equivalent, 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane, a 3,3-disubstituted oxetane motif, remains elusive, and its development is thus imperative (**Figure 1, C**). 3,3-Disubstituted oxetanes have been validated as surrogates or bioisosteres for *gem*-dimethyl or carbonyl functionalities, given their similar dipole, hydrogen-bonding properties and spatial orientation of the lone pairs, and concomitant improvement of metabolic stability, water solubility and reduced lipophilicity.^[22,35-40]

Figure 1. A) Importance of spirocyclic scaffolds in drug discovery. B) Currently accessible 1-oxaspiro[2.3]hexanes. C) This work: 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane as a desired new motif.

Design Plan

We hypothesized that 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes could be derived by intramolecular epoxidation of oxetane-substituted carbinols **1** (**Figure 2**). In contrast to the strategies developed for the synthesis of 1-oxaspiro[2.3]hexane and 1-oxa-5-azaspiro[2.3]hexane, epoxidation by strain-release of a “springloaded” bridgehead bond would however be precluded due to the presence of an oxygen atom, thus demanding a leaving

group driving intramolecular substitution. An intuitive retrosynthetic strategy entailing polar addition of an oxetane-bearing carbenoid to a ketone at first appeared attractive. At second glance, such carbenoid would, however, present a series of obstacles. First, the precursor would be challenging to prepare, and second, the carbenoid would presumably be unstable, as we have recently demonstrated the inherent instability of 3-oxetanyllithium.^[41]

To overcome these challenges, we postulated a switch from the polar to the radical domain. To this extent, Frustrated Radical pairs (FRPs), formed by single-electron transfer of certain Frustrated Lewis pairs, have recently emerged as a promising avenue for the functionalization of unactivated covalent bonds.^[42-50] For example, in 2023 Lin reported the first, and to the best of our knowledge hitherto only, functionalization of aliphatic C(sp^3)-H bonds leveraging a FRP derived from single-electron transfer between sterically encumbered hexamethyldisilazide anion and the *N*-oxoammonium cation 2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-1-oxo-piperidinium.^[51] Inspired by this report, we posit that in an analogous fashion, a sterically encumbered lithium amide could act as a reductant by single-electron transfer of benzophenone derivatives to form a transient *N*-centered radical and a persistent ketyl radical anion,^[52] reminiscent of a frustrated radical pair (**Figure 2**). Our hypothesis was supported by the known single electron transfer reactivity between lithium amides and benzophenone, reported more than four decades ago, although this chemistry has received little practical application in synthetic development.^[52-54] Literature precedent suggests that the *N*-centered radical would be a sufficiently potent hydrogen atom abstractor for the proposed (β)-hydrogen atom abstraction on 3-iodooxetane.^[51] This incipient C β -centered radical could then undergo a radical-radical coupling (RRC) with the persistent ketyl radical anion, forming carbinol **1** which is set-up for intramolecular epoxidation to the desired 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes. Although we were conscious of a potentially competing α -hydrogen atom abstraction, we were confident that selectivity on the four-membered ring could be tuned, as recently reported for the β -site-selective radical C(sp^3)-H functionalization of silacyclobutanes.^[55] Herein we report our studies on the development of a frustrated radical pair-type reactivity which culminated in the first synthesis of 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes, leveraging lithium amides not as conventional non-nucleophilic bases but rather as single-electron reductants and hydrogen atom abstractors, thus expanding their utility from the polar to the radical domain.

Figure 2. Design plan for the synthesis of 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes from 3-iodooxetane

Results and Discussion

At the outset, we tested the proof of concept and selected benzophenone, a non-enolizable, easily reducible bis-aryl ketone, as a model compound in combination with 3-iodooxetane. Upon optimization of the reaction conditions (see Supporting Information), we found that treatment of 3-iodooxetane (1 equiv.) and benzophenone (2 equiv.) in toluene with lithium 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine (LiTMP) (4 equiv.) at $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ proved optimal to afford epoxide **2** in 90% yield within two hours (**Table 1, entry 1**). Inversion of the stoichiometry affords epoxide **2** in only slightly reduced efficiency (**Table 1, entry 2**). Conducting the reaction in polar solvents (e.g., CPME or THF) (**Table 1, entry 3&4**), or at higher temperatures (**Table 1, entry 5**) had detrimental effects on the reaction outcome. Similarly, substitution of LiTMP with lithium amides containing α -hydrogens e.g., lithium diisopropylamide (LDA) or lithium dicyclohexylamide (LiNCy₂) (**Table 1, entry 6 & 7**) afforded diphenylmethanol *via* hydride-transfer to benzophenone as the major product,^[56,57] with epoxide **2** only formed in trace amounts. Use of LiHMDS also resulted in complete cessation of product formation (**Table 1, entry 8&9**). 3-Bromooxetane undergoes the transformation, although in reduced yield (**Table 1, entry 10**). To our delight, no competitive α -functionalization (i.e. α -hydrogen atom abstraction) was observed, thus we deduced that, according with literature precedent, complexation of the oxetane-oxygen to the lithium cation deactivates the α -position towards hydrogen atom abstraction.^[58–61]

Table 1. Optimization of the lithium-amide induced synthesis of 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes from 3-iodooxetane and benzophenone.

Entry	Deviation from standard conditions	2 (%) ^[a]
1	None	90
2	1 equiv. of benzophenone and 2 equiv. of 3-iodooxetane	84
3	THF as solvent	45
4	CPME as solvent	65
5	0 °C instead of $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	trace
6	LDA instead of LiTMP	trace
7	LiNCy ₂ instead of LiTMP	0
8	LiHMDS instead of LiTMP	0
9	LiHMDS instead of LiTMP, 0 °C instead of $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	0
10	3-Bromooxetane instead of 3-iodooxetane	40

[a] Yields were determined by ¹H NMR analysis using CH₂Br₂ as internal standard.

With a reliable protocol in hand, we evaluated the scope of ketones that could be employed to grant divergent access to various 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes (**Scheme 1**). In addition to benzophenone, a number of other aryl ketones bearing electron-withdrawing substituents gave the corresponding epoxides **3–6** in good yields. For example, epoxide **3** derived from 4-trifluoromethylbenzophenone was formed in 64% yield. Ketones bearing an ester functionality were found competent reactants affording the desired epoxides **4,5** in 51–67% yield. Interestingly, a second oxetane ring was tolerated in the reaction, and no competing events were observed. Remarkable, potentially SET-reducible alkynes were tolerated providing 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane **6** in 60% yield. Similarly, a series of halogen-containing derivatives **7–17** was prepared in moderate to good yields (34–86%), leaving the halogen handles available for further derivatisations (*vide infra*). It is interesting to note that an *ortho*-chloro substituent had mostly detrimental effects on the yield of the desired product (**13–15**) likely suggesting a dependence of the SET process from stereoelectronic effects. Moreover, the structures of compounds **4,8** and **12**, bearing respectively the ester functionality and a *para*-bromine substituent, were further confirmed by single crystal X-Ray diffractometric analysis.^[62] Interestingly an out-of-plane arrangement of the two aromatic rings was observed for all the structures.

Next, aromatic ketones bearing electron-donating substituents were tested. The reaction of phenylthio-substituted ketones yielded the desired epoxide **19** with 90% yield. Similarly, the presence of strongly electron-rich alkoxy substituents facilitated the formation of epoxides **20–23**, achieving yields up to 90%. It is worth noting that, in line with previous observations on similar motifs,^[29] during purification of these alkoxy-substituted 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes an acid-mediated rearrangement to dihydrofuran-3(2*H*)-ones was observed. This sensitivity towards acidic conditions of the 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane core has been exploited for further transformations (see **Scheme 3** for details). The use of other slightly electron-rich ketones such as 4,4'-dimethylbenzophenone afforded the desired product **18** in 91% yield. To our surprise, the reactions with 2,4,6-trimethylbenzophenone and 2,2',4,4'-tetramethylbenzophenone did not occur.

Having explored the scope of substituted benzophenones we sought to extend the methodology to accommodate other non-enolizable ketones as substrates. For example, 3-benzoylpyridine and chalcone afforded the desired products **24** and **25**, respectively in up to 42% yield. Next, to get more insights on the role of stereoelectronic factors, we investigated ketones with a locked conformation of the two aromatic rings.^[62] Locked fluorenone derivatives provided the desired epoxides **26** and **27** in reduced 31–34% yields, whereas less-strained thioxanthone produced the epoxide **28** in a higher 57% yield. Last, extension to mono-aromatic ketones was tested by reaction with trifluoroacetophenone derivatives. To our delight, epoxides **29–31** were produced in up to 83% yield, offering a new avenue towards trifluoromethylated oxygen-bearing SSHs.

Scheme 1. Scope exploration. Yields are quantitative ¹H-NMR yields. [a] Not isolated due to partial acid-mediated rearrangement on silica gel. See Scheme 3 for further information. [b] Using a modified procedure with ketone (1 equiv.), 3-iodooxetane (2 equiv.) and LiTMP (4 equiv.). [c] Over two steps; base-catalyzed intramolecular cyclisation was affected separately. See supporting information for detail.

Last, we explored substrates bearing biologically relevant natural products and drug molecules. As esters offered a useful anchor point, a series of naturally occurring and biologically active terpenes were introduced on the aromatic ring, including menthol, verbenol and borneol, affording the desired 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes **32-34** in up to 72% yield. Notably, the alkene-functionality of verbenol was tolerated in the presence of LiTMP. Furthermore, fenofibrate, a drug for the treatment of abnormal blood lipid levels, was successfully transformed into 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane derivative **35** in 51% yield.

After assessing the scope of this tactic to establish 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes as a new explorable chemical space, we sought to investigate more deeply the observed chemical reactivity. In our design plan (**Figure 2**), we hypothesized single-electron reduction from LiTMP to ketones to provide ketyl radical anion-containing FRPs as a key mechanistic step, and thus questioned if the variations in yield (e.g., benzophenone vs. fluorenone), as well as the complete cessation of reactivity upon small variations in the starting material (e.g., 4,4'-dimethylbenzophenone vs. 2,2',4,4'-tetramethylbenzophenone) could be to some extent correlated to the ease of reducibility of ketones with respect to the 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidide anion. Reduction and oxidation potential determined by cyclic voltammetry were chosen as measures of ease of reducibility of ketones and reductant strength of 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidide, respectively (see Supporting Information). The oxidation potential of LiTMP was determined to be 0.35 V, which is in line with oxidation potentials of other lithium amides and confirms its capability to act as a single-electron reductant.^[51] We then turned to investigating a possible correlation between ease of reducibility of ketones and the observed yield for the corresponding 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes, and the results are shown in **Figure 3**.

In order to avoid comparison of values from different sources for some previously reported reduction potentials,^[63] all reduction potentials shown in **Figure 3** were determined by us through cyclic voltammetry. Notably, the highest reduction potential is observed for 2,4,6-trimethylbenzophenone **J** (-1.92 V) and 2,2',4,4'-tetramethylbenzophenone **K** (-1.99 V), which both do not undergo the desired reaction, so that it is reasonable to conclude that a reduction potential of ca. -1.9 V represents a limit, prohibiting single-electron transfer by LiTMP to ketones below this value. In line with this, more easily reducible ketones **A – I** ($E_{p/2} > -1.8$) all undergo the desired transformation to 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes, although with varying yields. Highest yields are obtained for ketones **G – I**, with a reduction potential between -1.7 V to -1.83 V. The observed drop in yield for more easily reducible ketones **A – F** initially seems counterintuitive, so that we concluded that ease of reducibility to the ketyl radical anion is an important, yet not the sole governing factor. For example, some ketones are known to undergo a second single-electron reduction to the corresponding bis-anion,^[63a,64] which cannot participate in the desired radical-radical coupling. For more easily reducible ketones (e.g., **A & B**) this second reduction wave lies within the determined limits of reduction by LiTMP, so that we hypothesize that the ketyl radical anions are to some extent further reduced to the bis-anion, thus leading to a lower yield. In addition, stereoelectronic effects cannot be ruled out (e.g.,

halogen atoms in **D – F**, or ring-locked system in **B**^[65]), leading to potential destabilization or shorter lifetime of the ketyl radical anion intermediate.

Figure 3. Correlation between reduction potential of various ketones and the yield obtained for the corresponding 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes under our standard conditions. Reduction potential is expressed in V. Since some of compounds evaluated showed chemically irreversible reduction waves the reduction (cathodic) potentials are reported as the potentials at half the peak ($E_{p/2}$) instead of cathodic peak potentials (E_{pc}). CV measurements were carried out at 25°C in dry acetonitrile (MeCN) containing tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (0.10 M) as the supporting electrolyte at a 100 mV/s scan rate between -2.5 and +1.0 V, starting at 0 V in the positive scan direction. After each experiment, the potential of the Ag electrode was calibrated against the ferrocene/ferrocenium redox couple and converted to vs. SCE by adding 380 mV.

To further validate our design plan, several experimental probes and computational investigations were considered to rationalize the outcome of this transformation (see Supporting Information for full detail on mechanistic investigations) (**Scheme 2**). To further support the role of radicals in this mechanism, we considered a radical trap experiment (**Scheme 2, A**). Thus, in addition to our standard conditions, TEMPO was included as a radical trap. Upon inclusion of 3 equivalents of TEMPO, the reaction was somewhat suppressed to afford the desired product in 30% yield. However, when 4.5 equivalents of TEMPO were included (exceeding the quantity of LiTMP as a single-electron reductant), product formation was completely suppressed, suggesting a mechanistic pathway involving radicals. In addition, we detected by HRMS 1,1'-oxybis(2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine) **A**, arising from trapping of a 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidyl-radical with TEMPO, supporting that a single-electron transfer from the lithium amide to the carbonyl is indeed a feasible pathway under these conditions. This is in accordance with previous literature,^[52-54] and further supported by the deep blue/purple coloration of the reaction mixture upon addition of LiTMP. Next, we studied the mechanism of carbon-carbon bond formation between 3-iodooxetane and bis-aryl ketones (**Scheme 2, B**). We hypothesized that carbon-carbon bond-formation could proceed either *via* radical-radical coupling between the 3-iodooxetanyl radical and the ketyl radical anion, or addition of 3-iodooxetanyl

radical to the carbonyl. We thus performed a competition experiment between equal amounts of benzophenone and 2,4,6-trimethylbenzophenone, a bis-aryl ketone which we found to be non-reducible under our conditions. In this experiment, benzophenone-derived 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane **2** was formed as the sole product, the reaction with 2,4,6-trimethylbenzophenone did not proceed (product **B**). This indicates that radical addition to the carbonyl group is not a feasible pathway, hence suggesting that radical-radical coupling (RRC) pathway is most likely operational for carbon-carbon bond formation. An analogous experiment with an (under our conditions) non-reducible aldehyde corroborated this conclusion (see Supporting Information).

Last, we tested the role of 3-iodooxetane as we had hypothesized that site-selective hydrogen atom abstraction could be aided by stabilization through ring-strain imposed orbital overlap and the presence of an oxygen atom in the ring. We thus investigated the importance of these two factors (**Scheme 2, C**). With regards to the ring-strain, 3-iodotetrahydrofuran was tested as a strain-reduced substrate under standard conditions. Dihydrofuran **45** arising from elimination/C2-lithiation/electrophilic addition to benzophenone, was formed as the sole product, corroborating the role of the ring strain as requirement for the radical reactivity. Having confirmed the significance of ring-strain, we proceeded to test the impact of the ring-oxygen by replacement of 3-iodooxetane with 3-iodocyclobutane, and also in this case the expected epoxide **D** was not detected. We concluded that the ring strain and the presence of the oxygen atom render 3-iodooxetane inert to polar deprotonation and ideal for stabilization of the C β -centered radical. A rationale for these experimental observations is provided during discussion of our *in silico* investigations.

Next, we rationalized the site-selectivity for the hydrogen atom abstraction. During the optimization of this reaction, we were delighted, yet also intrigued, to find that the hydrogen atom abstraction was highly selective for the desired C β -position, despite lower calculated bond dissociation energy for the α -carbon-hydrogen bond. We had hypothesized that complexation of a lithium cation to the ring-oxygen would deactivate the α -position. To test this rationale, we computed the bond dissociation energy (BDE) values for the carbon-hydrogen bonds in question of the lithiated complex of 3-iodooxetane (**Scheme 2, D**), and found that the BDE for the α -carbon-hydrogen bond is indeed significantly raised (93.9 kcal mol⁻¹ vs 83.4 kcal mol⁻¹), whereas the BDE for the β -carbon-hydrogen bond is lowered (94.1 kcal mol⁻¹ vs 95.3 kcal mol⁻¹). Given that for the lithiated complex, the BDEs for C α – H and C β – H bonds are similar, we justified the high selectivity for the desired C β – H abstraction with the stability of the resultant radical (**Scheme 2, E**). DFT calculations show, that the C α -centered radical is delocalized and eventually leads to form highly strained oxetene **E**, probably prohibiting this pathway. The challenging C α -H abstraction on 3-iodooxetane is further confirmed by our finding that well-established α -selective photochemical HAT protocols failed to functionalize this position (see Supporting Information). On the other hand, in line with our experimental observations, desired C β -centered radical **F** was found to be stable. To further rationalize this, we conducted a comprehensive natural bond order (NBO) analysis on the

proposed C β -centered radical of lithium-complexed 3-iodooxetane (see Supporting Information for full detail). We found that the radical system is supported by multiple donor-acceptor interactions which reveal a complex network of electronic stabilization mechanisms that synergistically contribute to the radical system's overall stability. Wiberg bond indices (WBI) provided insights into the electronic structure, revealing significant electronic delocalization through the σ -framework. The iodine-carbon bond exhibits partial double bond character (WBI = 1.162) with pronounced α/β spin asymmetry, and combined with the donor-acceptor interactions, this indicates that the observed radical stability primarily arises from hyperconjugative effects and through-bond coupling rather than direct resonance delocalization through the oxygen center. The importance of the oxygen atom can be justified by close examination of the lone pairs through natural localized molecular orbital (NLMO) composition. Of particular significance are the contrasting hybridization patterns observed for the oxygen-centered lone pairs: lone pair 1 exhibits a mixed sp-hybrid character with substantial s-orbital contribution (s: 57%, p: 43%), whereas lone pair 2 manifests purely p-orbital character (p: 100%). This pronounced differentiation in hybridization patterns facilitates optimal orbital overlap configurations for hyperconjugative interactions while preserving the geometric constraints of the four-membered ring structure. This geometric constraint, while potentially introducing ring strain, appears to enhance through-bond electronic coupling mechanisms, contributing to the overall stability of the radical system. Electronic stabilization is predominantly achieved through sp-hybrid orbital interactions within the σ -framework, complemented by the π -type interactions associated with the radical center and iodine lone pairs. In summary, these findings demonstrate how the constrained ring structure paradoxically enhances electronic stabilization through optimized orbital overlap configurations, and thus provides rationale for our experimentally confirmed relevance of the ring-oxygen and ring-strain for this reaction (*cf.* **Scheme 2, C**). Last, we used DFT calculations to better rationalize the nature of the FRP between the tetramethylpiperidiny radical and the ketyl radical anion (**Scheme 2, F**). We thus located the covalent complex **G** between the two radicals, which indicates significant unfavorable steric hindrance. Indeed, the bond formation was calculated to be highly endergonic ($\Delta G = 11.3$ kcal mol⁻¹) with a moderate activation energy ($\Delta G^\ddagger = 15.8$ kcal mol⁻¹), so that we concluded that co-existence of these two species as a FRP, without covalent bond formation, was feasible.

Based on these experiments and literature precedent, the following plausible mechanism is proposed (**Scheme 2, G**). The reaction is initiated by single-electron transfer from LiTMP to the bis-aryl ketone, generating an *N*-centred radical, as well as a ketyl radical anion, reminiscent of a frustrated radical pair. These do not react with each other, due to an unfavorable Gibbs free energy of bond formation. The potent 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidiny radical subsequently site-selectively abstracts a hydrogen from the β -position of 3-iodooxetane, aided by deactivation of the α -position by complexation of the ring-oxygen with lithium cation, and the stability of the C β -centered radical. Although the hydrogen abstraction from the C β -position appears to be a slightly

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endergonic process ($\Delta G = 3.8 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$), the subsequent radical-radical coupling with the ketyl radical anion to furnish iodohydrin **1** is highly exergonic ($\Delta G^\ddagger = -11.1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta G = -25.3 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$). This negative free energy indicates a

strong thermodynamic driving force that favors the radical-radical coupling between these two intermediates. Iodohydrin then spontaneously or *via* base-promotion undergoes intramolecular ring closure (RC) to the desired 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes.

Scheme 2. A) – C) Control Experiments. D) – F) In silico investigations G) Proposed Mechanism

To conclude our study, we tested the robustness of this new oxygenated motif under different conditions. Our findings suggest that this SSH is stable under oxidative conditions, in the presence of transition-metals and under basic conditions. However, this motif seems to be sensitive under acidic conditions when an electron-rich group is the substituent of the oxirane ring. In fact, dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes containing electron-donating substituents **20-23** could be converted to the corresponding dihydrofuran-3(2*H*)-ones **36-39** by treatment with trifluoroacetic acid in high yields. In contrast, analogues that do not contain strongly electron-donating substituents were found stable towards treatment with acetic acid, boron trifluoride or Amberlyst 15. Moreover, the aryl-bromine bond of 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane **8**

could be engaged in a Buchwald-Hartwig amination with morpholine, initially affording intermediate **40**, which upon flash column chromatography on silica gel converted into dihydrofuran-3(2*H*)-one **41**. Under oxidative conditions sulfide-containing dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane **19** could be transformed into sulfone **42** by treatment with *m*CPBA in 76% yield, or into the corresponding sulfoximine **43** in the presence of PIDA in methanol in 50% yield.^[66,67] Furthermore, epoxidation of verbenol-containing 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane **33** was executed using *m*CPBA, affording derivative **44** in 79% yield, and with high stereoselectivity (ca. 9:1 dr).

Scheme 3. Downstream transformation of 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes. Ring expansion: TFA, THF, 0 °C to rt, 30 mins. Buchwald-Hartwig coupling: Pd₂(dba)₃ (3 mol%), XPhos (12 mol%), NaOtBu, PhMe, 100 °C. Sulfide oxidation to sulfone: *m*CPBA (2.5 equiv.), CH₂Cl₂, rt. Sulfide oxidation to sulfonamide: [NH₄][H₂NCO₂] (2 equiv.), PIDA (1.25 equiv.), MeOH, rt. Alkene epoxidation: *m*CPBA (1.3 equiv.), CH₂Cl₂, rt.

Conclusion

In conclusion we report the first synthesis of 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes leveraging the double role of LiTMP as a single-electron reductant and as a hydrogen atom abstractor. This dual role of lithium amides as a reagent in the radical domain is hitherto synthetically underexplored and should enable new avenues for further synthetic developments that further expand this concept. The obtained 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexanes are a novel strained spiro-heterocyclic motif, and we have showcased that a series of aromatic ketones are suitable substrates for this transformation, including lipid level reducing drug fenofibrate. Last, the validity of our mechanistic hypothesis was underpinned by a series of in-depth computational and experimental evidence, including cyclic voltammetry studies, offering new insights into lithium amide and oxetane chemistry. We expect that this radical strategy can be applied to other hetero-substituted four-membered rings as well as to suitable C-H donors. Investigations into this topic are underway in our laboratory and results will be reported in due course.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

Keywords: oxetane • strained spiro heterocycle • single electron reduction • radical-radical coupling

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Strained spirocyclic 1,5-dioxaspiro[2.3]hexane were synthesized via a lithium-amide induced single-electron transfer to a series of non-enolizable ketones generating a frustrated radical pair-like *N*-centered radical and a ketyl radical anion pair. This pair works synergistically to selectively abstract the β -hydrogen from 3-iodooxetane, initiating a radical-radical coupling reaction. In-depth computational and experimental investigations support the proposed mechanistic pathway.

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